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Evaluation of thermoelectric module production in light of current literature

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Abstract— The performance of thermoelectric modules, which directly convert thermal energy into electrical energy, is directly related to their manufacturing methods. Solid-state synthesis is the classic method used for the production of thermoelectric modules such as Bi₂Te₃ and PbTe, which are the most commonly used. However, while this method has the advantage of industrial scalability, it also has disadvantages such as limited grain control and high processing temperatures. Advanced sintering techniques, such as Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) and hot pressing, allow for the development of denser, finer-grained structures with higher ZT values in a shorter time. While fine microstructures are achieved through melt spinning with rapid solidification, nanoscale structure control can be achieved through alloying, sintering, and chemical precipitation methods. Thus, the production of new generation thermoelectric materials with nano-doped components can be achieved with lower thermal conductivity coefficients and consequently higher performance. According to general assessments, sintering techniques provide effective performance, especially in nanostructured thermoelectric materials. While high-performance structures can be achieved in the short term using sintering techniques, in the future, the use of hybrid structures will enable the development of lower-cost methods with higher industrial applicability. This study examines and interprets current production techniques for next-generation high-performance thermoelectric materials.

Keywords: Phase change materials, PCM, manufacturing techniques, sintering.

1. INTRODUCTION

In industry, homes, and vehicles, the high amount of waste heat released from heating stoves, hot water systems, machinery, ovens, and motors can be recycled in some cases where they have high temperatures. Although TEM applications are mostly common in cooling, electricity generation can also be achieved due to the Seebeck effect, which arises from the temperature difference between the two surfaces of the modules[1, 2]. Thus, in situations where this waste heat energy cannot be converted as primary energy, it is converted into electrical energy using thermoelectric materials (Tese). With the help of p and n-type semiconductors connected in series and the effect of the input heat, some electrons move to the free state, creating holes in

the module, and thus thermoelectric energy conversion can be achieved[3]. During heat transfer from a hot to a cold source, electrons in the module are transported via n-type semiconductors and holes via p-type semiconductors, generating an electric current within the internal structure. Although their efficiency is relatively low, the most important advantages of TEMs are their ability to work with all types of thermal sources, their direct electricity generation capabilities, their low maintenance requirements, silent operation, and long lifespan[4, 5]. These modules, which operate based on the Seebeck/Peltier effect, are of great importance in the field of converting thermal energy into electrical energy due to their advantages such as temperature control, quiet operation, high reliability, long lifespan, and environmental friendliness[6-9]. Furthermore, since waste energy is being utilized, theoretically this process represents a complete recovery regardless of efficiency [10, 11]. Thermoelectric generators (TEGs), formed by combining multiple thermoelectrical units (TEMs), contribute to the fight against global warming by preventing the release of high heat into the environment in addition to generating energy[6].

The first thermoelectric materials were bismuth tellurium, and this material is still widely used today[12, 13]. However, the problem is that modules produced with this material can only be used at an average temperature of 70°C, which has created a need for thermoelectric materials for higher temperatures[14]. It has been stated that different materials have different ZT coefficients at different temperature ranges within the 0-1000°C temperature range[10]. It has been stated that the ZT coefficient varies between 0.2 and 1.4 depending on the temperature range. While Bi₂Te₃ (T<150°C) has a higher ZT value at low temperatures, the ZT value increases up to 1.4 with increasing temperature up to 1000°C. Therefore, research has begun into high-temperature resistant materials such as La₂Te₃ and SiGe. Furthermore, in order to increase the ZT value of thermoelectric materials, the aim today is to reduce the thermal conductivity coefficients of materials by adding nanomaterials[15].

Since these newly developed materials are generally in powder form, the thermoelectric module (TEM) production techniques are shifting from traditional module production methods to new generation module production methods. Compared to traditional thermoelectric module production methods, it is possible to obtain thermoelectric materials with better mechanical properties through the use of sintering techniques. In general, for new generation materials produced in powder form, the most effective method is improving their mechanical properties through sintering. Given that presenting these methods in the same study is expected to contribute to literature research in this field, this study examines and interprets current production techniques for new generation high-performance thermoelectric materials.

2. THERMOELECTRIC MODULE MANUFACTURING METHODS

A thermoelectric module is based on the principle of electrically connecting multiple n- and p-type semiconductors in series and thermally connecting them in parallel (Figure 1). The number of n- and p-type semiconductors used varies between 200 and 300 depending on the module dimensions. After the electrical connections of the p and n legs are made using copper or silver material, the module assembly is generally completed using ceramic (aluminum oxide, alumina) or polymer substrates[16].

Figure 1. Thermoelectric module structure[17]

The performance of TEMs is directly related to their manufacturing methods. TEMs produced using commonly used classic thermoelectric materials such as Bi₂Te₃ and PbTe are generally manufactured using the solid-state synthesis method, known as the classical method. In the solid-state synthesis method, p- and n-type thermoelectric legs are produced by extrusion technique[18]. Narrowband infrared sensors based on PbTe materials operate in a temperature range of 140–150[19]. However, commercially available multi-stage thermoelectric module-based solid-state coolers are only suitable for cooling needs in the 300–200 K temperature range. Development of multi-layer solid-state coolers is necessary to ensure the stable operation of IR devices[18]. In a study using solid-state synthesis methods, samples with a length of 10mm and a diameter of 15mm were used. In this study, multilayer thermoelectric modules with an operating temperature $T_c < 150^\circ\text{C}$ were produced[18]. Indeed, it has been noted that multi-layer thermoelectric coolers have higher performance than single-layer ones.

Figure 2. Production of thermoelectric legs by hot extrusion technique, a) Hot extrusion technique, b) 30mm diameter Bi₄Sb₂Te₃ ingots[18]

Although this method has the advantage of industrial scalability, it also has disadvantages such as limited grain control and high processing temperatures. Generally, very high temperatures are required for reactions to occur in this method. This high temperature requirement increases energy costs. In this process, grinding, pressing, and lengthy annealing stages, as well as long-term studies for homogeneous phase formation, can sometimes take days. The non-homogeneity of powder mixtures reduces material performance. High-temperature sintering increases grain growth, which in turn reduces phonon scattering and increases thermal

conductivity. Increased thermal conductivity is undesirable. Second phases can form, especially in multi-component systems. The evaporation of volatile elements such as TE, Se, and Sb at high temperatures can cause changes in the composition. Conventional sintering may not provide sufficient density, and electrical conductivity may decrease due to porosity. High temperatures also make it difficult to maintain the nanostructure. However, in thermoelectric materials, nanostructures are used to reduce thermal conductivity. Because the resulting product is significantly affected by uncertainties in grinding time, pressing pressure, and temperature profile, the repeatability of the same product becomes difficult. Therefore, each resulting product has different properties. Since contamination can occur during the grinding process, the resulting impurities can cause changes in electrical properties. As an alternative to this method, new generation methods have been developed, such as powder metallurgy, mechanical alloying, spark plasma (SPS), sintering, screen printing, tape casting, cold spraying, solvothermal/hydrothermal methods, and melt spinning.

1. POWDER METALLURGY

In this method, thermoelectric materials such as bismuth telluride are first synthesized in powder form, then compressed by pressing under high pressure and densified by sintering in a controlled atmosphere. Powder metallurgy, in short, is the process of producing a part by preparing metal, ceramic, or thermoelectric powders, compressing them in a mold, and sintering them (combining them by heating). The basic stages of this method are powder production, mixing, pressing, and sintering.

Hot pressing and spark plasma sintering methods are widely used, particularly to obtain thermoelectric elements with high density and low porosity. After sintering, the resulting blocks are cut and processed to prepare p-type and n-type legs, their surfaces are soldered, and they are placed between alumina or aluminum nitride (ceramic) plates to form a thermoelectric module. This method is one of the most commonly used techniques in thermoelectric module production due to its low cost, high density, good electrical performance, and suitability for mass production. A summary graph of a study using this method is presented in Figure 3[20]. In this study, the powder was first prepared using the gas atomization method and then densified using spark plasma sintering (SPS).

Figure 3. Production of TEM by powder metallurgy method[20]

2. MECHANICAL ALLOYING AND SINTERING

In this method of TEM production, semiconductor thermoelectric material powders such as Bismuth Tellurium and Lead Tellurium are ground in a high-energy ball mill to obtain a fine-grained and homogeneous structure. The particles are reduced to nano or micron sizes through fracture and cold welding mechanisms during mechanical alloying. This increases phonon scattering, reduces thermal conductivity, and improves thermoelectric performance. The resulting powders are then subjected to hot pressing or Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) methods to increase density, reduce porosity, and obtain a more compact structure. After sintering, they are cut into p and n-type legs, and their surfaces are metallized. The thermoelectric module, with its electrical connections completed, is soldered between Alumina or Aluminum Nitride plates to obtain its final form. This method is used to obtain high-performance TEMs because it allows for nanostructure control and enables the achievement of high density and improved ZT values.

The disadvantages of this method include contamination from balls and cups during grinding, deterioration of electrical properties due to oxidation, formation of undesirable or unstable phases during prolonged grinding, grain growth leading to loss of nanostructure during sintering, increased porosity due to failure to achieve complete densification, stoichiometric ratio changes due to loss of volatile elements such as Te and Se, long processing time, increased costs due to high energy consumption, and the brittleness of the resulting materials, making them susceptible to cracking during thermal cycles. These factors can negatively affect

thermoelectric performance and especially the ZT value. Figure 4 presents a study using the mechanical alloying sintering method.

Figure 4. Mechanical alloying sintering[21], a) c) mechanical alloying, single-step spark plasma sintering to prepare TEM legs, assembly

3. SCREEN PRINTING

In this method of thermoelectric module production, the principle is based on transforming thermoelectric powders into a printable "ink (paste)," printing them onto a substrate in a patterned manner, and then sintering them to create functional legs. The process begins with mixing p and n-type thermoelectric powders with binders and solvents to form a viscous paste. This paste is then screen-printed onto a substrate such as ceramic or polymer using a stencil (mask) to create specific patterns. After printing, drying, and pre-bonding, high-temperature sintering is applied to establish electrical conductivity between the powder particles. This allows for the design of thin, thick, and dense thermoelectric legs. The resulting p and n-type thermoelectric legs are arranged to form electrically series and thermally parallel connections. Interconnections are added between the p and n-type legs using materials with high electrical conductivity, such as copper, to complete the TEM. This method offers advantages such as low cost, the possibility of producing in large areas, flexible device manufacturing, and suitability for mass production, while sintering quality and contact resistance control are critical parameters for high performance.

Figure 5. TEM production using screen printing method, a)[22], b)[16]

In a TEM (Temperature Control) production study using the screen printing method, silver electrodes were fabricated onto a ceramic substrate, then placed onto a template electrode. Thermoelectric materials were stacked on top of each other to form a galvanic double arm, sintered, and encapsulated. In this study, a screen printing plate was first designed to match the assembly method of the TEM. The screen printing plate was then pressed onto a ceramic

substrate of the same size via a sintering process, thus obtaining the first and second silver electrodes. The sintering process was carried out at 850-950°C for 30-60 minutes[23]. After these steps, buffer bonding layers were formed for the first and second silver electrode plates by applying solder paste with a thickness of 30-50µm (Figure 6a and b). Then, transparent mask plates with the same shape and size as the ceramic plates were created (No. 1 and No. 3). Appropriate p and n grooves were created on this mask according to the silver electrode pattern (Figure 6c and d). Figures 6e and f show the fitting of the first and second masks onto the silver electrode plates.

Figure 6. TEM production using screen printing method[23]

A mask representing p and n thermoelectric modules was fitted onto each electrode. These masks will utilize pre-prepared suitable p and n substrates. The p and n substrates were created by appropriately coating the previously obtained powders. The first and second thermoelectric

plates were stacked on top of each other and sintered in an inert atmosphere in an oven at a temperature range of 450-650°C. Thus, p and n type electrode thermocouples were obtained[23]. After obtaining the thermocouple handle and solder joint layer, the final step is drawing the red and black wires. The red and black wires are drawn into P-type and N-type electrodes respectively, coated with insulating material and insulating adhesive, and then the package is cured. According to the four preparation steps above, a laminated thermoelectric power generation module can be prepared. This method adopts the lamination principle, and the p and n thermocouple handles are prepared by coating thermoelectric material layer by layer onto an alumina ceramic substrate through a mask plate and by the sintering method. A thermoelectric power generation module is obtained by combining, sintering, and packing two types of thermocouple arms together. This method has several advantages compared to the traditional thermoelectric power generation module preparation process. Firstly, the method reduces many operations, effectively shortens the preparation time, and significantly increases the preparation efficiency. Secondly, it ensures low material loss and pollution-free preparation, and the preparation cost is significantly lower. Thirdly, the use of the layer-by-layer coating method can fully reveal the best thermoelectric value of each thermoelectric powder material and improve the thermoelectric power generation efficiency of the temperature difference power generation module.

The main disadvantages of screen printing is the inability to fully control layer thickness and homogeneity during printing, decreased electrical conductivity due to porosity and crack formation, shrinkage and adhesion problems during high-temperature sintering, resolution limitations in fine, defective prints, extreme sensitivity to ink viscosity and particle distribution, alignment problems in multilayer structures, and the generally lower density of thermoelectric legs compared to bulk materials; this can lead to increased electrical resistance and consequently decreased module efficiency.

4. TAPE CASTING METHOD

This method, a ceramic-like production technique, involves manufacturing powdered thermoelectric materials in the form of thin, homogeneous, and large-surface-area layers. P and n thermoelectric powders, such as bismuth tellurium and lead tellurium, are mixed with binders to form a fluid (slurry). This mixture is flattened onto a flat surface using a doctor blade to form a film strip of the desired thickness. The resulting structure is dried to allow solvents to evaporate and form a green strip structure. The resulting strips are cut, laminated if necessary, and then densified by sintering in a suitable atmosphere. Sintering increases the conductivity and mechanical strength of the material. P and n type thermoelectric components obtained by cutting from the resulting strips are arranged to form electrical series connections and joined

with metal interconnects. The final structure is placed between ceramic carriers such as aluminum nitride or alumina to give the TEM its final form.

Figure 7. Tape casting method [24].

The tape casting method offers advantages such as large-scale production, thickness control, multilayer structure creation, and low cost. However, shrinkage control and crack prevention during sintering present critical production challenges. The main disadvantages of this method include cracking and shrinkage during drying in thin ceramic or thermoelectric layers, inability to achieve homogeneous layer thicknesses, the possibility of binder and solvent residues leading to porosity after sintering, negative impact on electrical conductivity due to low density, difficulty in transporting brittle thin strips, delamination risk in layered structures, and loss of stoichiometry due to grain growth during high-temperature sintering, resulting in reduced mechanical strength.

5. COLD SPRAY METHOD

In the cold spray method, powdered thermoelectric materials are impacted onto a suitable substrate by a high-velocity gas fluid to form a solid block. Because the particles strike the surface with high kinetic energy, they undergo plastic deformation, forming a dense coating. P and n-type thermoelectric powders are impacted onto a metal substrate at supersonic speeds using a carrier powder such as helium or nitrogen. The resulting n and p legs are connected electrically in series and thermally in parallel using metal interconnects, and then mounted onto carrier plates such as alumina or aluminum nitride, thus completing the TEMs.

(a) Schematic of the cold-spray process, showing powder feed and gas handling. Note that the powder is injected after the expansion in the throat of the gun. (b) and (c) Depositions of Bi_2Te_3 bars on quartz and copper, respectively; the height of the material is approximately 3 mm. (d) Uniform deposition was achieved over the full surface by rotating the pipe during the spray process for lines of *p*- and *n*-type Bi_2Te_3 . Kapton tape prevented overspray from making direct thermal and electrical contact between the two electrodes.

Figure 8. TEM production by cold spray method[25]

The main advantages of this method are the low production temperature, minimal oxidation, and rapid formation of thick and dense coatings. However, optimization is required in terms of particle deformation control, electrical contact resistance, and the formation of a homogeneous p and n structure. The main disadvantages of this method is the need for expensive equipment for high-speed particle spraying, the hard and brittle nature of the resulting thermoelectric products, insufficient plastic deformation of the product and therefore inadequate adhesion, the formation of microcracks in the coating, the occurrence of high surface roughness, insufficient densification, increased process cost due to high gas consumption, and the possibility of cracking and delamination effects in thermal cycles due to residual stresses generated during spraying.

6. PLASMA SPRAY-THERMAL SPRAY METHOD

In the plasma spray method for TEM production, thermoelectric powders are partially melted in a high-temperature plasma jet and sprayed onto a substrate. A dense coating forms after rapid solidification. The prepared p and n-type thermoelectric powder materials are transported to a plasma torch using carrier gases such as argon or azore. In the plasma environment, some of the particles reach high temperatures of 1000-2000°C, melt, and are rapidly sprayed onto the substrate surface. The material impacting the substrate surface forms flat layers called splats. The stacking of multiple layers in this way creates a thermoelectric coating. The resulting p and n thermoelectric materials are processed to obtain thermoelectric legs, which are then connected electrically in series and thermally in parallel using metal connectors. This structure is usually mounted on alumina or aluminum nitride to form a module. The biggest advantage of this method is the high coating speed, thus allowing applicability to larger surfaces, and the ability

to produce thick thermoelectric layers. However, due to the high temperatures the material is exposed to, challenges such as phase distortion, oxidation, and difficulty in microstructure control necessitate precise optimization.

Figure 9. TEM production using plasma spray method[26]

HOT SINTERING

Powdered materials placed in a mold are heated to a temperature below their melting point and then combined under pressure to form a dense solid piece [27]. When a material is heated below its melting point before pressure, its atoms disperse, come into contact with each other, and the spaces between them decrease. This method, aimed at achieving a more robust structure, is used in the production of ceramics, metals, and some composite materials. Temperature and time must be carefully adjusted; otherwise, the material properties will be negatively affected. In this study, which aims to produce Al/Ti laminated composite, the goal is to impart superior properties to the material using the hot press sintering method[28]. The aim is to reduce thermal stresses and oxidation between Al and Ti by densifying the Al powders. In this way, a strong metallurgical bond is formed between Al and Ti, preventing the formation of coarse intermetallic phases. The microstructure and composition of the material can be easily adjusted with powder sintering methods.

SPARK PLASMA SINTERING

Spark plasma sintering, also known as SPS, is a sintering process based on the principle of rapidly converting powder materials into dense solids under heat and pressure. The most important advantage of this method is that it requires fewer processes and takes less time than traditional sintering[29]. Powdered materials are condensed under pressure with an electric current inside a graphite mold. The Joule heat generated by the electric current accelerates the relaxation and condensation. After the powdered material is filled into the mold, an electric current is applied in pulsed form under a vacuum or controlled atmosphere. Along with this, the applied pressure quickly produces a high-strength ceramic or metal part. Sintering is usually fast, completed within minutes. It is energy-efficient because it allows sintering at lower temperatures. Since the fine-grained structure is preserved, they have good mechanical and functional properties. Ceramics, alloys, composites, and some biomaterials are produced using

this method. The use of graphite as the mold material and the need for special equipment mean that this method cannot be directly applied to every material. Temperature, pressure, current, and time must be very carefully controlled.

RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Although traditional thermoelectric module production techniques enable the formation of structures with high purity and stability, they have significant disadvantages such as high energy consumption, obtaining a brittle material structure, and high cost. New generation thermoelectric production techniques positively affect material properties, reduce production costs, increase mechanical strength, and achieve higher energy efficiency. With new generation TEM production techniques, the aim is to increase electrical conductivity, reduce thermal conductivity, and produce modules with high mechanical strength, long lifespan, and flexibility over wide temperature ranges. In particular, thanks to features such as nano-doped materials, thin film technology, spark plasma sintering, and 3D printing, highly efficient, compact, and durable TEM production is becoming possible.

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